

Bibliography for data sources for LaMontagne et al. (Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B)

A bibliography of conifer reproduction data used in this study (modified from Pearse et al. 2017 (including data from Koenig & Knops 2000), and LaMontagne et al. 2020).

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